

RDM@SSM Curriculum

Research Data Management and Open Science for Social Sciences Researchers

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Founder	This curriculum has been designed and developed as part of a mandate from swissuniversities , specifically under the Open Research Data calls / Measure C2.2: RDM-Training in Curricula .
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This curriculum is designed for social science researchers from various disciplines and working with different methods and data types. It builds progressively from foundational knowledge to more advanced and specialist topics in Research Data Management (RDM) and Open Science.

While broadly applicable, certain parts of the curriculum, particularly those concerning data repositories and regulations, have been specifically curated for Swiss-based and European-based researchers.

A core, overarching component of this training is the continuous development of a comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP) throughout all modules. This global exercise will allow participants to apply theoretical concepts directly to their own research projects as the curriculum unfolds.

Indeed, the curriculum adopts a dynamic and interactive pedagogical approach throughout, designed to provide social science researchers with both foundational knowledge and practical skills. Learning is facilitated through a blend of direct instruction and active engagement. Participants will experience a variety of teaching strategies, including:

- **Presentations/Lectures:** Core concepts, theoretical frameworks, and policy requirements are introduced through structured presentations and lectures, ensuring a solid understanding of RDM and Open Science principles.
- **Interactive Discussions and Group Work:** To foster deeper understanding and peer learning, sessions incorporate extensive group discussions, where participants can share experiences, debate challenges, and collaboratively explore solutions related to data management, ethics, and sharing. Group exercises provide opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios.
- **Individual and Hands-On Exercises:** Practical application is central to the curriculum. Participants will engage in individual work, such as utilising online templates to develop their own DMPs, ensuring direct application of learned concepts to their research projects. Hands-on demonstrations and exercises, particularly for tools related to quality control, version control, and data citation, are integrated to build tangible skills.

- **Case Studies and Real-World Examples:** The curriculum uses relevant case studies from social science research to illustrate concepts, discuss ethical dilemmas, and demonstrate the practical implications of good RDM practices. Real-world examples, such as funder requirements and specific platforms (e.g., SWISSUbase), are used to ground the learning in contemporary research environments.

This multi-faceted approach aims to create an immersive learning environment where participants not only acquire knowledge but also develop critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, and a commitment to responsible and transparent research practices in the social sciences.

The course underwent two successful testing phases in 2024: one delivered online and another in person.

Day 1: Introduction to Research Data Management and Open Science in Social Sciences & Data Management Planning

Learning outcomes

By the end of the first session, participants will be able to:

1. Understand the importance of RDM and Open Science practices in social science research:
 - 1.1. Describe the evolving landscape of RDM and Open Science policies and mandates, particularly those relevant to social science research.
 - 1.2. Define Open Science and its core values and develop an understanding of the numerous dimensions of Open Science, and some of the tools and practices involved in it.
 - 1.2.1. Identify the different stages of the research data lifecycle.
 - 1.2.2. Explain the concept of research data and its role within the research process, both when data can be shared, and when sharing is not possible.
 - 1.2.3. Understand the basic principles of research data management.
 - 1.2.4. Articulate the benefits and opportunities associated with good RDM practices, including increased research transparency, reproducibility, collaboration, and impact.
 - 1.3. Identify stakeholders who benefit from effective RDM in research, such as researchers, research participants, funders, reviewers, and the wider scientific community.
 - 1.4. Understand the characteristics of open data, and in particular, explain the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and their importance in research data management during all stages of the research data lifecycle.
 - 1.5. Describe the potential benefits, challenges and difficulties of adhering to FAIR data principles for researchers and the wider research community, recognising the practices, values and norms of the social sciences and own discipline or subdiscipline.

- 1.6. Be familiar with the challenges and difficulties and potential limitations of other Open Science practices, such as open-access publishing and open-source code sharing.
2. In relation to Data Management Planning:
 - 2.1. Explain what a research dataset is and identify the range of data types.
 - 2.2. Identify the key challenges associated with poor data management practices, such as data loss, inconsistency, and difficulty in analysis and replication.
 - 2.3. Be able to plan ahead to prepare for potential data management pitfalls.
 - 2.4. Be aware of data management planning tools, support and guidance which are available to academic researchers.
 - 2.5. Be able to describe strategies for data management in collaborations, considering aspects like data ownership, sharing, and access control.
 - 2.6. Compare and contrast different funders' (e.g. Swiss and EU) data management planning requirements.
 - 2.7. Utilise online templates to identify and fill in the key elements of a DMP for a social science research project, including:
 - 2.7.1. Describing *what* data will be collected in their own project.
 - 2.7.2. Describing the allocation of resources (expenses and responsibilities) related to data management activities within their own research project.

Values and attitudes:

This part of the course fosters a sense of **professionalism and responsibility** for researchers in managing their research data. Participants will gain an appreciation for the **importance of data quality and transparency** in ensuring the credibility and trustworthiness of research findings. Participants will develop an appreciation for the principles of Open Science and its potential to advance knowledge and promote collaboration in the social sciences.

Session plan

Associated LOs	Teaching strategy	Strategy Description	Timing
Introduction	Round table	Participants will be asked to introduce themselves including their institution, position, field, current research project (or responsibilities related to RDM/OS). Introduction to the instructors and course structure.	30'
1.1-1.2	Presentation using slides	The instructor will describe the evolving landscape of RDM and Open Science policies and mandates, particularly those relevant to social science research. The instructor will define Open Science and its core values and develop an understanding of the numerous dimensions of Open Science, and some of the tools and practices involved in it. The instructor will identify the different stages of the research data lifecycle.	30'
1.1-1.2	Group discussion	Participants will engage in a guided group discussion to share and reflect on how they currently approach, or plan to approach, the different stages of the research data lifecycle within their own research projects. This will foster peer learning and allow for the identification of common practices and potential challenges.	N/A
1.2.3, 1.2.4, 1.4	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain the basic principles of research data management. The instructor will explain the characteristics of open data, and in particular, the FAIR data principles and their importance in research data management during all stages of the research data lifecycle.	25'
1.2.2, 1.2.4, 1.5	Group work, Group discussion	Participants will engage in group work. First, they will articulate the benefits and opportunities associated with good RDM practices, including increased research transparency, reproducibility, collaboration, and impact. Following this, as part of describing the potential benefits, challenges, and difficulties of adhering to FAIR data principles, they will undertake the 'FAIRness of a dataset' exercise (Veerle Van den Eynden (2020) Exercise:	40'

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		<p>FAIRness of a dataset. UK Data Service, UK. https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/app/uploads/exercise_fairdata.pdf). This involves using the online FAIR self-assessment tool by ARDC (https://ardc.edu.au/resource/fair-data-self-assessment-tool/) with provided example datasets (e.g., Kovacheva, S. and Demireva, N. (2018). DOI: 10.5255/UKDA-SN-853333 or Daniàn. J. et al. (2018). DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2549444). They will assess an existing dataset's Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability, noting how each aspect has been achieved (or not), and consider what could be done to make the datasets more FAIR. A subsequent group discussion will allow them to present their brief reports and explore these considerations further, recognising the practices, values, and norms of the social sciences and their own discipline or sub-discipline.</p>	
1.3, 1.6	Presentation using slides	The instructor will identify stakeholders who benefit from effective RDM in research, such as researchers, research participants, funders, reviewers, and the wider scientific community. The instructor will make participants familiar with the potential limitations of other Open Science practices, such as open-access publishing and open-source code sharing.	20'
1.3, 1.6	Group exercise, Class discussion	This exercise will involve participants identifying various stakeholders in research (e.g., researchers, funders, institutions, public) and discussing their roles and benefits in relation to Research Data Management (RDM) and Open Science. The discussion will further explore the practicalities, benefits, challenges, and limitations of implementing different Open Science practices like open access publishing and open-source code sharing, considering real-world scenarios.	45'
N/A	Presentation using slides	Introduction of final presentation and individual assignment.	5'
N/A	Individual work	Individual work on slides for presentation.	2h

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1.2.2, 2.1	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain the concept of research data and its role within the research process, both when data can be shared, and when sharing is not possible. The instructor will explain what a research dataset is and identify the range of data types.	15'
1.2.2, 2.1	Group discussion	Participants divided into four groups will be asked to share what data, research methods and datasets they generate and use, and whether these are the norm in their communities (research group, department, field).	15'
2.2-2.3	Presentation using slides	The instructor will identify the key challenges associated with poor data management practices, such as data loss, inconsistency, and difficulty in analysis and replication. The instructor will enable participants to plan ahead to prepare for potential data management pitfalls.	15'
2.7	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain LO 2.7, task 1 -> Utilise online templates to identify and fill in the key elements of a DMP for a social science research project: describing what data will be collected in their own project (DMP online template, description of what data will be collected).	15'
2.4	Presentation using slides	The instructor will make participants aware of data management planning tools, support and guidance which are available to academic researchers. The instructor will provide an introduction to the online DMP tool.	20'
2.7.1	Individual work	Completion of the relevant section of the online DMP based on participants' own research projects or example research project provided by instructors: Description of what data will be collected.	15'
2.6	Presentation using slides	The instructor will compare and contrast different funders' (e.g. Swiss and EU) data management planning requirements (SNSF vs EU DMP form).	10'

2.7.2	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain the second task related to LO 2.7, which involves utilizing online templates to identify and fill in the key elements of a DMP for a social science research project. This task specifically focuses on describing the allocation of resources, including both expenses and responsibilities, related to data management activities within the participants' own research projects, making use of the DMP online template for resource allocation.	10'
2.5	Presentation using slides	The instructor will describe strategies for data management in collaborations, considering aspects like data ownership, sharing, and access control.	10'

Reading list:

- I. Lecturers' slides
- II. Data Management Expert Guide: European Diversity. CESSDA.
<https://dmeg.CESSDA.eu/Data-Management-ExpertGuide/1.-Plan/European-diversity>
- III. "FAIR Principles." <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.
- IV. Mons, Barend, et al. "Cloudy, Increasingly FAIR; Revisiting the FAIR Data Guiding Principles for the European Open Science Cloud." *Information Services & Use* 37, no. 1 (January 1, 2017): 49–56. <https://doi.org/10.3233/ISU-170824>
- V. Open Science Training Handbook. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1212496>
(<https://open-science-traininghandbook.gitbook.io/book>)
- VI. Research Data Alliance "FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines". DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>
- VII. Wilkinson, M.D. et al. "The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship." *Scientific Data* 3, no. 1 (March 15, 2016): 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- VIII. UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMH8546>

Homework assignment, if any:

Completion of relevant parts of the DMP as began during the day as well as continuation of preparation for the final presentation.

Tools, resources to be shared with participants:

- DMP Online <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/> :

“DMPonline is a user-friendly, web-based tool designed to empower researchers in developing data management and sharing plans. It provides the latest funder templates and best practice guidelines, making it easy for users to create high-quality DMPs.

Researchers will find a wealth of custom guidance and example answers within the tool, providing them with the support and guidance they need to develop their DMP. The DCC, research funders, and many research organisations contribute to this resource. Users can also browse the growing list of public DMPs published by other tool users for inspiration.”

- Examples of national RDM and ORD policies:
 - US National Science Foundation <https://new.nsf.gov/funding/data-management-plan>
 - Australian Research Council
<https://www.arc.gov.au/about-arc/arc-strategies-and-policies/international/research-data-management>
 - Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft <https://www.dfg.de/en/basics-topics/basics-and-principles-of-funding/research-data> - <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/172098/b08fcad16f1ff5ddca967f1ebde3a8c3/guidelines-researchdata-data.pdf>

Day 2: Data Collection & Active Data Curation

Learning outcomes

By the end of this session, participants will be able to:

1. Explain the importance of systematic data collection methods and standardised procedures in social science research.
2. Utilise online templates to identify and fill in the key elements of a DMP for a social science research project, including:
 - 2.1. Designing a data collection plan that is well-organised, efficient, and minimises the risk of errors – explaining how data will be collected in their own project, and how data will be documented (data collection instruments, data collection procedures, and, if applicable, data coding schemes).
3. Understand that data curation is a complex and resource-intensive, yet vital process for research.
4. Understand options for maximising data reuse and implement best practices for active data curation, including:
 - 4.1. Explain the importance of clear and detailed documentation for future reference and data sharing.
 - 4.2. Describe and apply best practices for creating a clear and consistent data structure to facilitate data retrieval and management, including appropriate file- and folder-naming.
 - 4.3. Compare relevant quality control techniques that allow for identifying and addressing errors, inconsistencies, and missing values within their research data (e.g., identifying and correcting typos or inconsistencies in data entry, handling missing data points through imputation or exclusion, detecting and resolving outliers in quantitative data).
 - 4.4. Explain the importance of data format and data version control, and use basic tools for format/version control on Microsoft 365 or Google Drive, as well as version control systems (like Git, particularly suited to code) to track changes and revert to previous versions if necessary.
 - 4.5. Choose appropriate file formats for different data types, considering factors like long-term usability, interoperability, and accessibility.

Values and attitudes:

This session emphasises the importance of **meticulous data handling** as a cornerstone of **rigorous research**. Participants will develop a critical eye for data quality and understand that systematic data collection and active curation practices are essential for ensuring the **reliability and reproducibility** of research findings. By actively cleaning, structuring, and documenting their data, researchers contribute to **increased transparency** and facilitate future analysis by themselves or others. This fosters a culture of **professionalism and accountability**, where researchers take ownership of the integrity of their data. Additionally, the session will reinforce the **collaborative nature** of Open Science. Effective data curation practices not only benefit the researcher but also make data more readily **reusable** by colleagues, ultimately contributing to the advancement of knowledge within the social sciences.

Session plan

Associated LOs	Teaching strategy	Strategy Description	Timing
1, 3	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain the importance of systematic data collection methods and standardised procedures in social science research. The instructor will explain that data curation involves a complex and resource-intensive set of procedures, yet it is vital for research.	20'
2	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain LO 2, task 1 -> Utilise online templates to identify and fill in the key elements of a DMP for a social science research project: designing a data collection plan that is well-organised, efficient, and minimises the risk of errors (Data collection plan - how the data will be collected: data collection instruments, data collection procedures, and, if applicable, data coding schemes).	10'

2.1	Individual work	Completion of the relevant section of the online DMP based on participants' own research projects or example research project provided by instructors: Data collection.	20'
2.1	Class discussion	Present the difficulties that you encountered in designing the data collection process for your specific case.	20'
4.1-4.2	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain the importance of clear and detailed documentation for future reference and data sharing. The instructor will describe and apply best practices for creating a clear and consistent data structure to facilitate data retrieval and management, including appropriate file- and folder-naming.	20'
4.1, 4.2	Group exercise, Group discussion	Participants will undertake the 'Data documentation' exercise (by Veerle Van den Eynden, Scott Summers, and Stuart MacDonald, 2018 https://dam.ukdataservice.ac.uk/media/622181/exercise_documentation.pdf). This exercise focuses on understanding how to best prepare and document research data for future reuse, appreciating it from the perspective of a new user unfamiliar with the dataset. This will be followed by a group discussion on best practices for clear and detailed documentation and creating a consistent data structure, including appropriate file- and folder-naming.	30'
2	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain LO 2, task 2 -> Utilise online templates to identify and fill in the key elements of a DMP for a social science research project: designing a data collection plan.	15'
2.1	Individual work	Completion of the relevant section of the online DMP based on participants' own research projects or example research project provided by instructors: Data documentation, completion of whole DMP tasks for the first two days.	1h

4.3	Presentation using slides	The instructor will compare relevant quality control techniques that allow identifying and addressing of errors, inconsistencies, and missing values within their research data (e.g., identifying and correcting typos or inconsistencies in data entry, handling missing data points through imputation or exclusion, detecting and resolving outliers in quantitative data).	20'
4.3	Group work, group discussion	Participants will engage in group work. They will read and annotate an interview transcript (transcript from a PhD project on aging and midlife. The researcher gave the audio recordings to different transcribers with varying ranges of transcription experience). Participants read (individually) through the transcripts and try to note any issues and what the researcher might have done differently. Then, they can compare your notes within the group. At the end of the exercise, the original transcript with annotations is presented for comparison.	30'
4.4	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain the importance of data format and data version control and use basic tools for format/version control on Microsoft 365 or Google Drive, as well as version control system (like Git, particularly suited to code) to track changes and revert to previous versions if necessary.	20'
4.3, 4.4, 4.5	Class discussion	Whole class discussion about issues on data formats and data version / errors / missing data.	10'
4.4, 4.5	Individual exercise, Group discussion	Participants will engage in group work, imagining they are outsourcing transcription for 30 in-depth interviews on a sensitive topic. This exercise focuses on developing guidance notes for transcribers and a transcriber confidentiality agreement, including appropriate wording and key clauses, to address practicalities and ensure data security. This will be followed by a whole-class discussion comparing approaches (Corti, L., Van den Eynden, V., Bishop, L., & Woollard, M. (2019). Exercise 5.3. In <i>Managing and sharing research data: A guide to good</i>	30'

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Reading list:

IX. Lecturers' slides

Homework assignment, if any:

Completion of relevant parts of the DMP as began during the day as well as continuation of preparation for the final presentation.

Tools, resources to be shared with participants:

- Recommended Data formats
<https://www.reading.ac.uk/research-services/-/media/project/functions/research-and-enterprise-services/documents/rda-recommendedfileformats.pdf>
- Examples of DMP for SNSF projects
https://www.usi.ch/sites/default/files/storage/attachments/servizio-ricerca-dmp_examples.pdf
- Folder and File Naming Convention – 10 Rules for Best Practice:
<https://exadox.com/en/articles/file-naming-convention-ten-rules-best-practice>
- Example transcription instructions
<https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/app/uploads/ukda-example-transcription-instructions.pdf>

Day 3: Data Ethics & Privacy

Learning outcomes

By the end of this session, participants will be able to:

1. Understand the ethical and legal challenges around personal/sensitive data.
 - 1.1. Understand the difference between ethics and law.
 - 1.2. Understand the general legal and normative framework.
2. Recognize personal and sensitive data.
3. Learn to know which laws apply and when.
 - 3.1. Learn how to apply legal standards.
4. Learn how to design and obtain informed consent.
5. Distinguish between anonymisation and pseudonymisation.
 - 5.1. Learn how to design a data anonymisation strategy.
 - 5.2. Learn to distinguish between different types of identifiers.
 - 5.3. Learn about the main data anonymisation techniques.
6. Learn how to control access to data as an additional layer of protection.
7. Learn how to build a risk management strategy around personal/sensitive data.
8. Understand when and why to consult an Ethics Committee.
9. Know how to incorporate elements relating to ethics and data protection into their DMP.

Values and attitudes:

This session highlights the paramount importance of **research ethics** and **data protection** in social science research. Participants will gain a deeper understanding of the legal and ethical frameworks that govern the collection, storage, and use of research data,

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particularly when dealing with personal and sensitive information. Through discussions on informed consent, anonymisation, and pseudonymisation, participants will develop a commitment to **respecting participants' privacy and rights** and upholding the **highest ethical standards**. The session will also emphasise the importance of **transparency** and responsible data management practices. By ensuring proper data governance, researchers demonstrate **accountability** and build trust with research participants and the wider community. Finally, this part of the course will foster a **critical approach** to Open Science, encouraging participants to consider the ethical implications alongside the potential benefits of open data sharing.

Session plan

Associated LOs	Teaching Strategy	Strategy Description	Timing
Introduction	Round table	Participants will briefly introduce themselves and share their initial feelings or experiences regarding ethics and data protection (e.g., scared, enthusiastic, bored, confident). Introduction to the module.	20'
1.1	Presentation using slides	The instructor will provide an overview of the history of research ethics through examples, present its fundamental principles, and outline the differences and convergences with the legal framework. Participants are encouraged to adopt a critical, reflective approach.	20'
1.2	Presentation using slides	The instructor will present the legal framework for data protection, providing an overview of existing legislation.	20'
2	Presentation using slides, Class discussion	The instructor will provide a theoretical and practical presentation, including concrete examples, of what constitutes personal and sensitive data. Participants will be made aware that social science research often involves the collection of sensitive data, followed by a class discussion.	60'

3	Presentation using slides, Class discussion	The instructor will present the main laws applicable in Switzerland, tools for identifying relevant laws abroad, and an approach to determining which law applies and when (e.g., GDPR, HRA). This will be followed by a class discussion.	20'
3.1	Presentation using slides, Class discussion	The instructor will present, based on frequently asked questions, the main practical implications of the current legal framework concerning consent, processing of public data, working with minors, storage, archiving, and dissemination of datasets. This will be followed by a class discussion.	40'
4	Presentation using slides, Class discussion	The instructor will define informed consent, present the criteria for valid consent, and discuss procedures for obtaining consent. The session will include an evaluation of excerpts from consent forms and a presentation of exceptions concerning consent. This will be followed by a class discussion.	30'
5.1	Class discussion, Presentation using slides	Participants will share their experiences with anonymisation as a warm-up, discussing why data should be anonymised. The instructor will then explain the importance of anonymisation and its main challenges, defining anonymisation and related concepts (distinguishing it from pseudonymisation), and outlining when and how to apply an anonymisation strategy.	15'
5.2	Presentation using slides, Class discussion	The instructor will identify the main steps and key mechanisms behind anonymisation, and distinguish between direct, strong indirect, and weak indirect identifiers, followed by a short class exercise. This will be followed by a class discussion.	15'
5.3	Presentation using slides	The instructor will explain the main data anonymisation techniques for both quantitative and qualitative methods and guide participants on how to choose them.	15'
6	Presentation using slides	The instructor will describe different access conditions (open access, access upon registration, restricted access, embargo) and how to control access to data as an	15'

		additional layer of protection, including how access can be controlled with SWISSUbase.	
7	Presentation using slides, Class discussion	The instructor will present a general approach to risk management. Participants will be encouraged to always carry out a risk assessment to define the necessary degree of protection and security for their data management, emphasising a pragmatic approach. This will be followed by a class discussion.	30'
8	Presentation using slides, Class discussion	The instructor will present the different types of existing ethics committees (compulsory and voluntary), outlining procedures for submitting data projects to cantonal ethics committees (when projects are submitted to the HRA) and providing an example of a university commission. Participants should be able to anticipate the time, resources, and project progress required for ethics commission review.	15'
9	Individual work	Participants will work on filling in questions related to ethics and legal considerations within a Data Management Plan (DMP) template.	30'

Reading list:

- X. Diaz, P. (2022). Data protection: legal considerations for research in Switzerland. *FORS Guides*, 17, Version 1.1, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2022-00017>
- XI. Diaz, P. (2021). Introduction: Archiving Qualitative Data in Practice: Ethical Feedback. *Bulletin of Sociological Methodology/Bulletin de Méthodologie Sociologique*, 150(1), 7-27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0759106321995678>
- XII. Diaz, P. (2019). Ethics in the era of open research data: some points of reference. *FORS Guides*, 3, Version 1.1, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2019-00003>
- XIII. Diaz, P., Stam, A. (2019). How to draft a DMP from the perspective of the social sciences, using the SNSF template. *FORS Guides*, 7, Version 1.1, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2019-00007>

- XIV. Stam, A., & Kleiner, B. (2020). Data anonymization: legal, ethical, and strategic considerations. *FORS Guides*, 11, Version 1.1, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2020-00011>
- XV. Stam, A, Diaz, P. (2023). Qualitative data anonymisation: theoretical and practical considerations for anonymising interview transcripts. *FORS Guides*, 20, Version 1.1, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2023-00020>
- XVI. Kleiner, B. & Heers, M. (2024). Quantitative data anonymisation: practical guidance for anonymising sensitive social science data. *FORS Guides*, 23, Version 1.0, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2024-00023>

Homework assignment, if any: No homework assigned apart from completing their DMP

Tools, resources to be shared with participants:

Day 4: Data Storage & Security

Learning outcomes

By the end of this session, participants will be able to:

1. Understand the increasing importance of properly storing and protecting research data:
 - 1.1. Describe the main threats to research data.
 - 1.2. Describe the regulatory and compliance issues that drive the adoption of data protection measures.
2. Evaluate and select appropriate storage solutions for research data, considering factors such as accessibility, security, cost, and long-term viability.
 - 2.1. Describe the main data storage technologies available on-premise and in the cloud, and their relative characteristics, such as capacity, speed, cost.
 - 2.2. Identify the data storage requirements for different types of data (e.g., text, audio and video recordings) at different stages of specific research projects.
 - 2.3. Select the most appropriate storage technologies in relation to the requirements identified.
3. Explain the importance of data security and identify key security threats in research data management:
 - 3.1. Describe the main conceptual dimensions of information security, such as confidentiality, integrity and availability.
 - 3.2. Adopt a risk-based approach to security by identifying and evaluating the main threats to the security of research data.
4. Gain a basic knowledge of the formal approaches to information security, in order to understand the formal requirements from funding agencies and contractual partners, and to interact with these parties as well as security specialists and auditors.
 - 4.1. Describe the purpose and key concepts of ISO/IEC 27000 family of standard and NIST Cybersecurity Framework
5. Design effective technical and organizational measures to protect research data, including:
 - 5.1. Adopt appropriate authentication and authorization measures, e.g., strong passwords and two-factor authentication.

- 5.2. Design access control, e.g., defining access group for different types of data and different stages of the research data lifecycle.
- 5.3. Adopt encryption mechanisms and products, e.g., for protecting sensitive data.
- 5.4. Define backup strategies, procedures and responsibilities based on identified risks, e.g., institutional or cloud backup, backup cycle and verification.
- 6. Document in the relevant sections of the Data Management Plans:
 - 6.1. The approach adopted for the storage and security of research data.
 - 6.2. The storage requirements for research data of specific projects.

Values and attitudes:

This session emphasises the importance of **data stewardship** and **responsible data management**. Participants will develop and increased awareness about and a critical eye for data security. Participants will also understand the obligation to protect research data from unauthorised access, loss, or corruption. By adopting best practices in storage and security, researchers demonstrate **accountability** and contribute to the **reliability and trustworthiness** of their research findings. Additionally, the session promotes a culture of **preparedness** by equipping participants with knowledge and skills to recover from potential data loss incidents.

Session plan

Associated LOs	Teaching strategy	Strategy Description	Timing
1, 1.1, 1.2	Round table, Presentation using slides	Participants will introduce themselves, including their position and current projects. The instructor will then use slides to present a motivation for increased attention to data storage and security through recent cases of data security incidents in universities. The instructor will also describe the session's objectives and methods (Presentation using	30'

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		slides and activities).	
2, 2.1, 2.2, 2.3	Presentation using slides, Group work, Discussion of results	The instructor will present the main technologies for data storage and their characteristics using slides. Participants will then engage in group work to quantify storage space requirements for a specific research project (either their own or a fictitious one provided by the instructor as a fallback). This will be followed by a discussion of their results.	30'
3, 3.1, 3.2	Presentation using slides, Group work, Discussion of results	The instructor will present the main concepts related to information security, including confidentiality, integrity, availability, threat, vulnerability, and risk, using slides. The instructor will also present the main concepts about information security risk management, covering risk identification, analysis, evaluation, treatment, and controls. Participants will then engage in group work to identify, analyse, and evaluate risks for a specific research project (either their own or a provided example). This will be followed by a discussion of their results.	45'
4, 4.1	Presentation using slides	The instructor will present the key aspects of the ISO 27000 family of standards and the NIST Cybersecurity Framework using slides. The instructor will also provide examples of controls from these two sources that are applicable to research data management.	30'
5, 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4	Presentation using slides, Group Work, Discussion of results	The instructor will present various data protection measures using slides, including authentication and authorisation, access control, encryption, backup strategies, and additional measures such as physical security, data deletion, and incident response. Participants will then engage in group work to identify technical and organisational measures applicable to a specific research project. This will be followed by a discussion about the level of application of these measures in different institutions and research groups, and a general discussion of results.	60'

Reading list:

- XVII. Lecturer's slides
- XVIII. List of references

Homework assignment, if any:

-

Tools, resources to be shared with participants:

- XIX. Activity worksheets (single Excel file with multiple tabs)
- XX. Fictitious project ("Project Sigma")

Day 4: Data Preservation & Sharing

Learning outcomes

By the end of this session, participants will be able to:

1. Understand the Value and Impact of Data Sharing and Open Science
 - 1.1. Explain benefits like transparency, collaboration, and recognition.
 - 1.2. Describe successful examples (e.g., ESS, WVS, COVID-19, climate models).
2. Identify and Discuss Common Concerns About Open Data
 - 2.1. Recognize ethical, professional, and practical objections to data sharing.
 - 2.2. Formulate responses to common concerns.
3. Plan for Data Reusability Using the 10-Step Guide
 - 3.1. Outline essential steps for making data reusable.
 - 3.2. Evaluate personal or project-level practices using the checklist.
4. Apply the FAIR Principles for Data Management
 - 4.1. Define and classify FAIR principles.
 - 4.2. Evaluate data practices against FAIR criteria.
5. Develop Strategies for Data Preservation and Long-Term Access
 - 5.1. Distinguish between data storage and data preservation.
 - 5.2. Identify suitable platforms and formats for long-term access.
 - 5.3. Understand the role of professional repositories in ensuring data longevity.
6. Analyze Trends and Challenges in the Data Archiving Landscape
 - 6.1. Describe the evolving Swiss and international data archiving infrastructure.
 - 6.2. Identify trends such as professionalization, certification, and AI tools
7. Evaluate the Role and Services of Data Repositories

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- 7.1. Describe repository features, standards, and services.
- 7.2. Compare repository options based on discipline and data needs.

Values and attitudes:

This session fosters a commitment to **openness** and **collaboration** within the research community. Participants will gain an appreciation for the value of data preservation and sharing as a means to maximise the impact and longevity of research. By creating high-quality metadata and using persistent identifiers, researchers contribute to a **transparent research ecosystem** where data is discoverable and reusable by others. Navigating legal and funder requirements ensures compliance and promotes responsible research practices. Participants will gain further appreciation for the benefits of data sharing and explore how controlled vocabularies and data citations promote **interoperability** and **reusability** of research data. Ultimately, the session encourages participants to view their data as a valuable resource that can contribute to advancing knowledge beyond the scope of their immediate research project.

Session plan

Associated LOs	Teaching strategy	Strategy Description	Timing
1, 1.1, 1.2	Interactive exercise, slides	The instructor will present key benefits and global examples of open science. Participants will create and present short “elevator speeches” in groups, synthesizing the key reasons for open science.	30’
2, 2.1, 2.2	Discussion, slides	Participants will discuss shared concerns raised during the presentation and reflect on how these affect their own work. The instructor will moderate, providing counterpoints and facilitating peer input.	30’

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3, 3.1, 3.2	Slides	The instructor will introduce the 10-step-guide to make data reusable. The importance of this topic is explained using a comic strip.	30'
4, 4.1, 4.2	Slides and interactive quiz	The instructor will explain the FAIR principles with practical examples. Participants will then complete an interactive quiz to match guiding principles to FAIR categories (Findable, Accessible, etc.).	60
5, 5.1, 5.2, 5.3	Slides, guided discussion	The instructor will contrast short-term storage vs. long-term preservation and introduce best practices. Participants will discuss their own preservation experiences, focusing on challenges and what worked well.	15'
6, 6.1, 6.2	Mini lecture	The instructor will present key developments (e.g. Swiss ORD strategy, CoreTrustSeal, Connectome).	15'
7, 7.1, 7.2	Live Demo, Q&A	The instructor will demonstrate using SWISSUbase to deposit and access data. A follow-up Q&A session allows participants to ask specific questions about repository use and suitability.	30'

Reading list:

No reading list.

Homework assignment, if any:

Answer the questions regarding data sharing and preservation in the assigned DMP

Tools, resources to be shared with participants:

FORS Guide No. 21: <https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2023-00021>

SWISSUbase info website on Sharing data and preservation: <https://info.swissubase.ch/resources/?sr=2306#Share>

SWISSUbase User Guides: <https://info.swissubase.ch/resources/?sr=929>

SWISSUbase repository: <https://swissubase.ch>

15 guiding principles on FAIR: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Day 5: Reproducible Research and Data Citation

Learning outcomes

By the end of this session, participants will be able to:

1. Explain the core principles of reproducible research and their importance in ensuring the credibility and reliability of research findings.
2. Describe different strategies for disseminating research findings, including data, in a clear and accessible manner.
3. Identify and apply tools and best practices to make research findings transparent and replicable.
4. Identify appropriate data reuse licences.
5. Understand best practices for data citation in social science research.
6. Critically evaluate the potential impact of RDM and Open Science practices on research careers and incentives, including the emergence of research data journals.

Values and attitudes:

This part of the course fosters a culture of **research transparency**, **research reproducibility** and **scientific rigor**. Participants will develop a commitment to designing and conducting research in a way that allows others to verify and replicate their findings. Recognising the potential impact of RDM and Open Science on research careers and incentives, this session encourages participants to embrace responsible data management practices as a means of **maximising the impact** of their research contributions.

Session plan

Associated LOs	Teaching strategy	Strategy Description	Timing
1	Interactive drawing exercise and Presentation	Participants will engage in an interactive drawing exercise where they are asked to reproduce a monster by following step-by-step instructions. This icebreaker activity will demonstrate the challenges of reproducibility, as the resulting drawings are often varied despite identical instructions.	20'
1	Concept explanation	The instructor will present key definitions of core concepts such as reproducibility, replicability, robustness, and generalisability. The aim is to ensure that participants understand the foundational concept of reproducibility and transparency.	20'
1, 6	Presentation using slides	The instructor will deliver a concise lecture tracing the historical origins of the reproducibility crisis in the social sciences. The instructor will explain how the lack of reproducibility of some key studies, using examples from different disciplines, sparked significant controversy and led to the reorientation of research practices. The instructor will also describe the roots of Open Science and highlight how various best practices fit into its broader framework, contributing to greater research transparency.	40'
2-3, 6	Hands-on demo, Case study, Group discussion	The instructor will present various replication tools and preregistration platforms through practical demonstrations. Participants will engage with interactive polls (e.g., using tools like Mentimeter) and group exercises (i.e., case studies discussed in small groups) during the demonstrations to assess their understanding and stimulate discussion on the effective use of these tools.	1hr

4-5	Presentation using slides	The instructor will present and lead a discussion on the key concepts and best practices related to data citation in plenum. The Survey of Health, Aging, and Retirement (SHARE), a European study known for its rigorous data citation standards, will be used as a practical example.	20'
N/A	Class discussion	The instructor will lead a class discussion for wrap-up and feedback.	10'

Reading list:

Munafo, M.R., Nosek, B.A., Bishop, D.V., Button, K.S., Chambers, C.D., Sert, N.P., Simonsohn, U., Wagenmakers, E., Ware, J.J., & Ioannidis, J.P. (2017). A manifesto for reproducible science. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 1.

Tools, resources to be shared with participants:

- **Video presenting preregistration**
UKRN (2023). Preregistration & Registered Reports – a UKRN animated primer[Video]. Youtube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h0Pin-OUIS4>
- **Preregistration platform**
As predicted. (n.d.). Home. Retrieved August 28, 2024, from <https://aspredicted.org>
- **FORS Replication Service.** (n.d.).Home. Retrieved August 26, 2024, from
<https://resources.swissubase.ch/replication/deposit-your-replication/>
- **FORS Guides**
Bornatici, C. & Fedrigo, N. (2023). Data Citation: How and Why Citing (Your Own) Data. *FORS Guides*, 19, Version 1.1, 1-15.
<https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2023-00019>
- Heers, M. (2020). Pre-registration and registered reports. *FORS Guides*, 9, Version 1.1, 1-11.
<https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2020-00009>

- Heers, M. (2021). Replication in the Social Sciences. *FORS Guides*, 16, Version 1.1, 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.24449/FG-2021-0001>